

VERBALIZATION OF THE "COLOR" CONCEPT AS AN EXAMPLE OF POETRY PIECES

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ANNOTATION

In this article, comments on the linguistic and cultural concept studied in the framework of linguo-cultural studies are presented. Various color concepts are discussed. The meanings of the colors involved are explained through examples.

Key words: *concept, understanding, linguistic culture, lexeme, association, frequency.*

Currently, along with all fields, the science of linguistics is developing more and more. In world linguistics, before the text was approached from a syntactic structural point of view, since the 21st century, the analysis by means of linguocultural, linguocognitological, sociolinguistic and psycholinguistic principles has increased.

It is known that the term "concept" was used in linguistics for the first time in S.N. Askoldov's article "Concept and word" written in 1928. [1;62] Concept is a copy of the Latin word *conceptus* - "notion". The concept has two aspects. On the one hand, culture enters the mental world of a person in the form of a concept, on the other hand, a person enters the culture with the help of a concept and sometimes influences it. While this term was used in linguistics as a synonym for the word concept until the 80s of the last century, today it can be seen that its interpretation has expanded compared to the term concept. [2;44] Among the many definitions given to the concept in Russian linguistics, the definition put forward by V.A. Maslova was evaluated by Professor N. Mahmudov as a more accurate reflection of reality. According to him, the concept "is a semantic structure in which linguistic and cultural identity is recorded

and which describes the owners of a certain ethno-culture in one way or another." Professor N. Mahmudov writes about the study of concepts in linguistic and cultural studies: "In linguistic and cultural studies, a lot of attention is paid to the problems of expression of the concept, when you get acquainted with the Internet materials, for example, you can see that this direction is extremely widespread in linguistic studies in Russia it is possible, it is difficult to enumerate the works in this regard". [3;9] So, the concept is considered the most actively used unit in linguistic and cultural studies. The concept as a linguistic and cultural unit expresses the unique aspects of the culture of this or that nation. [2; 45] Let us dwell on the concept of "color" that represents such aspects.

The lexeme of color (f. - hue, color, paint) is a substance used for painting; represents the meaning of paint. There are different colors from nature, and each of them served to perform a certain task in the works of representatives of classical literature. Various forms of the concept of colors are reflected in the works of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. For example:

Tell me, if you see a weak branch in the flower,

If you miss the yellow grape, you will see the leaves of the garden. [5;116]

The yellow lexeme involved in the given stanza means the meaning of the color of things like straw, silk, and gold. [4;482] In classical literature, this color has been used since ancient times to express the state of being in love. It is known that the state of a person suffering from a disease can be felt through his appearance and face. Yellowing of the face means that a person is not well and is a sign of illness. Also, referring to Khazan by means of yellow color has increased the power of meaning. The concept of yellow is associated in this way in the works of representatives of classical literature. There are many ghazals using this lexeme in Babur's works.

My face is as yellow as blood.

Bahar range, bihamdillah, ulusdin I saved myself. [5;118]

In the following stanza, he used the yellow lexeme to mean that he is in a bad state of being in love and that he is suffering from an illness. Through this, the artist was able

to more clearly reflect the sufferings of a lover. In this example, the meaning of "a face as yellow as a fox" is embedded in the content of the stanza. This association of the color yellow can be felt in the consciousness of the Uzbek people through the proverb "If your motherland is safe, your color will not be straw." Because folk proverbs are the means of summarizing the cultural life and lifestyle of this nation.

He has a black eye and a dimple

It's a mistake to blame someone else.[5;13]

The lexeme "black" in the old Uzbek language is distinguished by its polysemy and frequency of use compared to other adjectives denoting color. Historically, the meaning of this word has expanded. In Turkish, the word black means "big", "big", "magnificent", "great", "powerful", "strong", "pure", "pure", "land", "earth", "darkness". "ki", "north" expressed such meanings. In Navoi's works, the concept of black includes the concepts of black balo (disaster), black soul (suffering soul), black pain (black disease), black money, black grief, axtar black (unhappiness), and bird. there is [6;91] In Babur's ghazal, the lexeme of black was connected to the lexeme of eye, forming the combination of black eye, and thereby reflecting the meaning of lover. Black color is associated with the meaning of lover.

My head was full of smoke, jealousy, and black hair.

Let's get on your feet, you sarvinoz. [5;18]

The concept of black in this stanza embodies various meanings. Combined with the lexeme of hair, it means black hair, i.e. yor, and combined with the lexeme of smoke, it means the blackness of the smoke coming out of jealousy, as well as the meaning of black hair. He associated three different meanings in one place.

Make me spit with anger and anger!

May the sea be deprived of your grace!

O Lord, look at my face and make it white.

Whatever you like, do it! [5;59]

Black and white colors are used in a contrasting sense in the rubai written by Babur. The contradiction in the concepts of these two colors is embedded in the content

of a person with good qualities and a person with bad vices. The concept of black color is associated with the meaning of a sinful servant, and the concept of white color is associated with the meanings of a righteous servant, free from guilt and mistakes.

*Your white face fell far away,
My two eyes turned white.
Your mouth is so sad that I am scolded,
I will walk without dying, I will not die.[5;90]*

The white spot taken from the given example was used in two places and created a homonym. The artist has associated the meaning of beauty on earth under the concept of white color used in the first stanza, while in the second stanza he has reflected the meaning of disease that is visible through the concept of white color. Whiteness in the eye, leukoma - clouding of the cornea; usually, it is observed when the membrane is damaged or when inflammation, wounding process appears in it. This disease limits the ability to see.

In short, the notion of a concept is a unit that can summarize a number of meanings. The concept of various colors in nature associates new meanings depending on the situation of use and the artist's skill. In addition to being an active unit of linguistic culture, the concept reflects the culture and mentality of peoples.

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